

SOCIAL SCIENCES

AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON INVESTORS' AWARENESS ABOUT MUTUAL FUNDS AND THEIR JUDGING CRITERIA OF FUNDS' QUALITIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11397074>

Abstract

The present study examines the investments made through individual investors in mutual funds. The study attempted to analyse the objectives and factors considered by individual investors while investing in mutual funds and also to identify the criteria adopted by investors to judge the qualities of investors. The data was collected through online, via email, and in-person meetings. The questionnaire was distributed among investors having at least two years of investments in mutual funds. The sample respondents' demographic data were evaluated using ranking and percentage techniques as part of the data analysis process. A five-point rating scale was used to evaluate the level of knowledge regarding mutual fund investments and the associated attributes of mutual funds. The research concludes that individual investors consider the performance record of mutual funds while investing. They also consider the return and safety of investing their hard-earned money in mutual funds. The study proposes that Asset Management Companies develop strategies effectively to meet investors' expectations and maintain their confidence in mutual fund investments.

Keywords: Mutual funds, Awareness of investors, Factors of investment, Fund's qualities.

1. Introduction

Investor knowledge and skill in making the appropriate number of investments in the proper securities at the appropriate times is critical to the success of any investing activity. A well-thought-out investment can provide consistent income and capital growth and satisfy investors' financial needs (Bhalla, 2008). An investor must exercise judgment while choosing investments, a skill learned via education and real-world experience. Investing in financial assets might result in economic loss for those needing more information and expertise about the financial market's operation (Das et al., 2016). That is why people require expert guidance when choosing the kind of investment to make; otherwise, they will only put their money into the financial market if they lose their hard-earned resources (Guillemette et al., 2017).

Financial markets are essential to a nation's economic growth. They promote investment activity in the economy by facilitating the sharing of limited resources by shifting them from investors to borrowers (Jureviciene et al., 2012). Mutual funds combine the money of numerous participants with a common trust-based financial objective (Kaur, 2018). The funds obtained are used to purchase securities, including shares and debentures, on the financial market. The quantity of money invested and the units' net asset value determine how many units investors receive. The amount of money received is distributed among the investors based on how many units they own. A mutual fund is an investment that meets the demands of the average person. It is an indirect type of capital market investment with tax benefits, low cost, expert management, liquidity, and diversity (Pellinen et al., 2011 & Chawla,

2014). The main goal is to reduce the risk involved in the capital markets to maximise investment rewards. The lowest unit cost is one of the most prevalent characteristics of mutual fund units. Mutual funds have advanced significantly as an investment choice since the Unit Trust of India (UTI) introduced the country's first mutual fund in the middle of the 1960s (Trivedi et al., 2017).

The primary factor influencing the investors' choice of suitable investment among the several investment outlets is their financial objective (Ranganathan, 2006). Investing in the stock market is one of the best options for investors in this situation. However, the primary issue of investors is how best to distribute the available assets across various investment possibilities (Kumar, 2020). It can be difficult for investors to find a suitable investment opportunity that fits their investment objectives, lowers future risk, and guarantees a respectable rate of return and earnings on their investment. Financial markets consistently growing more productive in the investing space by providing more appealing options for financial stakeholders. Trades in securities require a thorough understanding, skill set, and expertise from investors due to the distinctive features of the instruments that may be sold in the market. They accept the risk of losing money if the improper kind of security is chosen to make smart investing choices at the wrong moment. As a result, stock market investing is very difficult for most individuals. According to various studies conducted in this context by Asker et al. (2015), Sharma (2019), and Chernenko et al. (2021), mutual funds are the best option for individual investors to invest in securities since they provide a reasonably

priced way for acquiring diversified, well-managed investments.

A mutual fund is a type of collective investment vehicle that combines the capital of multiple investors and allocates it among government securities, money market instruments, bonds, and stocks. Expert fund managers capitalise the money collected in mutual fund investments by investing it in shares, bonds, and various other securities in accordance with the scheme's investment objective. A scheme's "Net Asset Value," or NAV, determines how much income or gains will be given to each investor proportionately following the deduction of any applicable taxes and levies (Tripathy, 2007). According to SEBI (Mutual Funds) Regulations, 1996, mutual funds are incorporated in India as trusts under the Indian Trust Act of 1882.

Mutual funds' primary goal is to invest saved cash in securities under appropriate schemes so that they are safe and yield respectable returns (Alamelu & Indhumathi, 2017). Baral et al. (2016) suggested that marketable securities with guaranteed liquidity, minimal risk, and other maximum tax savings for the investor are the securities in which mutual fund money is invested. Considering the background information above, an investment portfolio is defined by the terms 'investment' and 'portfolio'. An investment is a financial commitment undertaken to earn a favourable rate of return. The return on an investment will match the risk the investor takes if it is done correctly (Alexander, 1998). So, it contains three elements, i.e., return, elements of return, risk, and time factor. Conversely, portfolios are collections of assets held in a diversified way to minimise risk and guarantee maximum returns (Bergstresser et al., 2002). Therefore, decision-making expertise is required while choosing financial assets for investments to maximise returns while minimising risk (Ben-David et al., 2022). To put it briefly, a mutual fund is an accumulation of funds given by multiple participants under the supervision of a qualified fund manager. Fund managers, also called portfolio managers, carry out the mutual fund's choice to lower risks and provide higher returns. Therefore, choosing, acquiring, and managing financial assets are all part of portfolio management.

The term portfolio refers to a collection of financial instruments or assets held by an individual or a corporate body to reduce risk and maximise return. Before the publication of the work of Markowitz (1952), it was widely accepted that the best portfolio, securities, ideally from various industries. By selecting firms' investments in different sectors, the assets would be open to different influences. So, the inadequate execution of some of the securities would be outweighed by the excellent work of others (Busse, 2006). This causes the portfolio's overall performance to show less variability over time than it would if all the securities were from the same industry. This will eradicate the majority of the unsystematic risk of a portfolio if the quantity of securities in the portfolio is below the systematic risk level. At this stage, Markowitz could create a system to lower the portfolio's risk below the systematic level (Riley & Chow, 1992). The trade-off between risk and return lies at the heart of all investing decisions.

Though they are only sometimes prepared to take on the risk of achieving the high return they desire, all rational investors expect an adequate return. Often, the emphasis is exclusively on the records, ignoring the risks of investing in security. Investors who recognise all the risks associated with security investing will need help to maintain profitable returns (Tripathy, 2007). Mutual funds have shown their ability to deliver the goods in this situation. The idea behind mutual funds was to pool people's resources and use them to buy a combination of government and corporate securities. Mutual fund shareholders eventually receive dividends, interest, and capital gains from the operators of the mutual fund, who actively oversee this portfolio of securities (Vidal-Gareia et al., 2018).

2. Review of Literature

This literature study aims to describe the level of awareness among individual mutual fund investors and to pinpoint the qualities and elements other researchers have determined to be critical to the mutual fund's performance. Leon and Aprilia (2018) suggested a connection between investors' investment behaviours and their propensity for taking risks, as well as their personality traits, educational background, income, and financial situation. These investor traits were shown to be significant predictors of mutual fund perception and knowledge (Ul-Hameed et al., 2019; Ramaswami et al., 1992; Heena, 2015). The findings also show that personality and education are unimportant and have little bearing on how much money individual investors will make. Ahmed et al. (2022) determined the relationship and influence of demographic characteristics on investment decisions, and the writer concluded that age plays a significant role in investment. Kaur (2018) provided that their wealth and level of education influence investors' knowledge and impression of mutual funds. The study by Gupta et al. (2011) investigated investors' attitudes towards mutual funds and fixed deposits. Bishnoi (2014) focused on the substantial correlation between different investment returns, their respondents' occupational group, gender, age, income, marital status, place of residence, and level of education. When Parihar et al. (2009) looked at the connection between investment in mutual funds and demographic traits, they discovered that most investors thought well of mutual funds.

Numerous research has been conducted to determine the elements that influence investors' investment behaviours and their preferred avenues of investment (Chambers & Schlagenhauf, 2005; Gomez et al., 2024; Lee et al., 2019). Rehan et al. (2018) proposed that investors' preferences and attitudes towards their investment decisions and objectives are influenced by age, gender, income, and education. Sireesha and Laxmi (2013) suggested that peer group, age, and gender impacted investment decisions. Investors prefer their money to remain safe and secure rather than multiplying and becoming liquid. Rehan et al. (2018) examine various demographic characteristics that influence an investor's degree of awareness regarding mutual funds and other factors that influence the investor's perception and propensity to invest in mutual funds. Ahmed et al. (2022) describe that age and income negatively

correlate with the beta, but demographic characteristics like education, location, and experience have favourable correlations with the beta in multiple regression results. The assessment of mutual fund performance was given an additional dimension by Pavithra et al. (2023), which also helped to clarify which investment strategy was best suited for which fund. Ballestero et al. (2004) tackle the issue of choosing a mutual fund portfolio by looking for a ranking system based on compromised properties to derive utility boundaries from investor preference statistics.

According to research by Maheswari et al. (2022), most investors know mutual funds. Investors use money invested in mutual funds to reduce financial risk, save taxes, and ensure a consistent return in the future. It enables investors to diversify their holdings over various securities even with limited financial resources (Kwon et al., 2020). Rathnamani (2013) states that investors like mutual funds since they offer high returns with minimal risk, safety, and liquidity. However, contrary to these findings, Rajasekar (2013) points out that mutual fund investors are presumably apprehensive about their investments' safety, growth, and liquidity. A mutual fund's quality of returns is primarily determined by several variables, including the stocks that make up the portfolio (Agarwal & Pradhan, 2018). In a seminal article, Kaur et al. (2013) argue that investors believe stock market investing is complicated and hazardous, while they view mutual funds as flexible investment options and effective asset management firms. Investors choose mutual funds for their tax advantages, high returns, and safety (Anjum & Saini, 2011).

Mutual funds are accessed through a vital financial brokerage, as noted by Mishkin and Eakins (2015), which pools the capital of multiple small investors by selling their fund shares and using the proceeds to purchase assets. Arathy et al. (2015) depict that mutual funds serve as a means of access for regular investors with modest deposits to invest in large enterprises. Nicolescu et al. (2020) investigate the behaviour of mutual fund investors and assess the extent to which decisions are informed by knowledge by looking at a variety of relevant aspects. Walia et al. (2009) informed, that investors will feel more at ease participating in mutual funds and will be better equipped to choose mutual fund schemes based on their risk tolerance. Ranganathan (2006) argued that people lacking the necessary time, financial literacy, or expertise cannot make wise investment decisions. Kozup et al. (2008) also suggest that investors can make better use of financial information if they possess a high degree of understanding. Prathab et al. (2013) found that investors in India possess a considerable degree of knowledge regarding mutual funds and view them as a secure investment option that yields great returns and increases their wealth with minimal risk. In India, the mutual fund sector is expanding rapidly. Tripathy (2006) argue that mutual funds educate middle-class individuals in both urban and rural areas about the advantages of investing in the capital market through secure and profitable channels.

Tripathi and Japee (2020) state that most individuals stay aware of mutual funds, but relatively few invest in them. According to his findings, a Systematic Investment Plan (SIP) is preferred by 75 per cent of respondents. The participants know the stock market's operation and are aware that the Asset Management Company (AMC) makes investments in the stock market. Choi et al. (2020) propose that financial investments include buying shares, post office savings certificates, debentures, insurance policies, and other financial instruments to use the proceeds to generate income in the method of interest, dividends, premiums, pensions, benefits, or an increase in the value of the capital (Mishra, 2011). Investors can access various investment opportunities to place their money (Kohli & Devi, 2022). However, investors choose different investment routes depending on expectations and financial knowledge (Singal & Manrai, 2018). Chernenko et al. (2021) identify that mutual funds that take more reliable funding remain more likely to make investments. Ippolito (1992) claimed that investors are willing to put money into funds or schemes that have produced positive returns. Most investors are drawn to funds or schemes that are outperforming the worst. Ul-Hameed et al. (2019) argued that an investor's psychology influences mutual fund selection for investment and withdrawal, whereas Maity et al. (2023) point out that risk-return and knowledge awareness are the two main perceptual elements that prevent investment in mutual funds. Raman and Budhiraja (2016) identified retail investors' investment patterns, focusing on the mutual fund sector. They discovered that the rate of return connected with the investment option is the most crucial element for all age groups. Baker et al. (1977) recommended that investors should act wisely by considering the risk/return tradeoff. Saini et al. (2011) emphasised that investors are primarily drawn to the scheme's stability and past performance while selecting a mutual fund scheme. Other factors that affect their decision-making comprise the scheme's portfolio, entry/exit loads, and dividend history. Regardless of the amount invested, mutual funds provide an investor with a policy to engage in the capital market through expert fund management services (Arathy et al., 2015).

3. Research Gap

In the light of the aforementioned literature, most of the research on investors examined the socioeconomic factors, awareness and perception of mutual fund investors. Most investors have favourable opinions and perceptions of mutual funds. To get appropriate returns, they strongly desire to invest in mutual funds. However, the influence of investor awareness, preferences, and quality on mutual fund investments has not been fully addressed. To fill this gap, it would be relevant to study the awareness of individual investors in mutual funds and the criteria adopted by investors to judge investment qualities.

4. Objectives of the study

The present study is undertaken with a view to (i) analysing the objectives of investments made by individual investors in mutual funds, (ii) identify the factors considered by them while investing in mutual funds, (iii) study their awareness about investments in mutual

funds; and (iv) evaluate the criteria adopted by them to judge the qualities of mutual funds.

5. Methodology

The research is empirical in nature, and the data was collected from individual investors with at least two years of investment experience in mutual funds. A questionnaire was used to execute the survey. The target investors were given a questionnaire, which was also collected online, via email, and in-person meetings. Mutual fund investors were the researcher's target group because they have a greater propensity for saving and are more knowledgeable about available investment possibilities. After distributing 900 questionnaires using a convenient sampling method, it was determined that 428 mutual fund investors' responses could be used for the research. Investors have demonstrated their incapacity to recall the decision-making process, leading to problems with missing data or non-responses. Such investors' responses were not considered. Data was gathered for the study from various occupational groups, including professionals, self-employed individuals, government and private sector employees, own-business owners, and retirees. The sample respondents' demographic data were evaluated using ranking and percentage techniques as part of the data analysis process. A five-point rating scale has been devised to evaluate the level of knowledge regarding mutual fund investments and the associated attributes of mutual funds.

6. Data Analysis and Interpretation

The respondent profile shows that men were more involved in investing and financial activities than women were, with men comprising 63.8 per cent of the sample compared to 36.2 per cent of female respondents. Those who were married (73.8 per cent) were

found to be more active than those who were single (23.4 per cent). Younger respondents, constituting up to 21 per cent of the sample total, were primarily between the ages of 20 and 30. Sixty-one per cent of respondents were graduates, post-graduates, or had taken professional courses. Employees from private companies participated at the largest rate (57.2 per cent), followed by those from the government (17.1 per cent). This suggests that the risk and uncertainty of working in these fields may have led these people to look for other sources of income. 59.1 per cent of respondents had a monthly income of up to Rs. 1,00,000, 22.5 per cent had a monthly income of up to Rs. 2,00,000, and 18.5 per cent of respondents had an income of more than 2,00,000 rupees. This shows that even though mutual fund schemes needed a smaller commitment than other investment outlets, persons from lower income categories contributed more to them.

6.1 Objectives of investment

Investing is placing money into something that has the potential to increase in value, generate income, or both. Investing your resources in assets with illiquidity or investment risk enables them to become investments. These investments assist you in accumulating wealth that you can utilise for various purposes, such as a retirement fund, emergency fund, home purchase, kid education funding, etc. You will need to invest more money as you proceed in life. Growing obligations will require more money to be invested. This study illustrates investment goals for emergencies, children's schooling, construction efforts, children's marriage, fund accumulation, and post-retirement needs. The data acquired based on investment objectives are shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1

Objectives of investment			
Objectives of Investment	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank
Meet contingencies	3.79	1.342	2
For children's education	3.52	1.339	4
House construction	3.00	1.450	6
For purchase of Assets	2.86	1.457	7
Marriage of children	3.19	1.369	5
Accumulate Funds	4.21	1.210	1
Meet requirements after retirement	3.58	1.306	3

Source: Result of primary data analysis

The results displayed in Table 1 illustrate the investment objectives of mutual funds. Based on the statistical findings, investors' primary goal is to accumulate funds (mean 4.21, standard deviation 1.210, rank 1). Meet contingencies (mean 3.79, standard deviation 1.342, rank 2) is the next most important objective the investors consider. Meeting requirements after retirement (mean 3.58, standard deviation 1.306, rank 3) is also an important objective for individuals. The fourth and fifth criteria for investment objectives given by the investors are for children's education (mean 3.52, standard deviation 1.339, rank 4) and marriage of children (mean 3.19, standard deviation 1.369, rank 5). The sixth and seventh objectives of investments are for house construction and purchase of assets. Hence, it can be inferred that individual investors always give im-

portance to the accumulation of funds and meeting unexpected events in the future. Least importance is given to the purchase of assets and construction of houses.

6.2 Factors considered while investing in mutual funds

Investors place a great deal of attention on their investment selections in the financial markets since there are numerous variables that must be considered and their impact must be evaluated. However, investors may make better and more educated judgements if they remain current on market trends, economic situations, and personal circumstances. By doing this, they can safeguard their financial future and meet their financial objectives. This study demonstrates the need to consider many factors while making investments, including yield, risk, safety, liquidity, simplicity of use, and transaction costs. The data acquired based on the factors considered are shown in Table 2 below:

Table 2

Factors Considered While Investing			
Factors	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank
Return	4.67	0.809	1
Risk	4.01	1.050	3
Safety	4.12	0.982	2
Liquidity	3.89	1.115	5
Ease of Investment	3.96	1.157	4
Transaction Cost	3.57	1.295	6

Source: Result of primary data analysis

The findings in Table 2 highlighted the factors individual investors consider while investing in mutual funds. The statistical findings demonstrate that return (mean 4.67, standard deviation 0.809, rank 1) is the most crucial element that investors consider when making an investment decision. The second most significant element that investors consider is safety (mean 4.12, standard deviation 0.982, rank 2). Individual investors also consider Risk (mean 4.01, standard deviation 1.050, rank 3). Investors place ease of investing (mean 3.96, standard deviation 1.157, rank 4) and liquidity (mean 3.89, standard deviation 1.115, rank 5) as their fourth and fifth considerations. When making investment decisions, the transaction cost is seen as the least important aspect (mean 3.57, standard deviation 1.295, rank 6). Thus, it follows that individual investors

typically prioritise return and safety on investment while making investment decisions. The chosen investment's transaction cost is seen as having the least significance.

6.3 Awareness of Mutual Funds

Today's financial markets require much awareness, including current market movements and economic forecasts. This kind of expertise necessitates ongoing information gathering and a passion for economic growth. One may become aware of the circumstances in which they are more or less reluctant to trade if they tend to monitor market events and show interest in financial matters. The following assertions, which are provided in Table 3, are used to assess the study's findings regarding mutual fund awareness.

Table 3

Awareness of mutual funds			
Awareness	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank
Mutual Funds are the ideal option for small investors.	4.21	1.082	6
It is easy to invest in mutual funds.	4.40	0.864	1
It is easy to monitor investments with mutual funds.	4.28	0.923	4
Mutual Funds are like investing in any other financial product.	3.77	1.154	8
Returns from mutual funds depend upon the market performance.	4.36	0.949	2
Some categories of MF provide tax benefits.	4.22	1.049	5
Mutual Funds help to reap the benefits of capital market investments.	4.18	0.954	7
SEBI protects the interest of unit holders.	4.31	1.028	3

Source: Result of primary data analysis

The results presented in Table 3 depict awareness of investments in mutual funds. The investors receive information about mutual funds from the electronic media, print media, agents and brokers, and friends and relatives. In this source of information criteria, electronic media stands first. Most information about mutual funds is received from electronic media. While considering the level of awareness about mutual funds among individual investors, the most important criterion is that it is easy to invest in mutual funds (mean 4.40, standard deviation 0.864, rank 1). Returns from mutual funds depend upon the market performance (mean 4.36, standard deviation 0.949, rank 2), the next most important criterion the investors consider. SEBI protects the interest of unit holders (mean 4.31, standard deviation 1.028, rank 3) and is also considered the third important criterion by investors in mutual funds. Investors ranked fourth in the ease of monitoring investments in mutual funds (mean 4.28, standard deviation 0.923, rank 4). The fifth criterion points to tax benefits provided by investments in mutual funds (mean 4.22, standard deviation 1.049, rank 5). The sixth and seventh objectives of investments are that mutual funds

are an ideal option for small investors and that mutual funds help to reap the benefits of capital market investments (mean 4.21, standard deviation 1.082, rank 6) and (mean 4.18, standard deviation 0.954, rank 7). It is the least important and ranked eighth, as investing in mutual funds is like investing in any other financial product.

6.4 Criteria adopted to judge the qualities of Mutual Funds

To know about the criteria adopted by individual investors to judge the qualities of mutual funds, some of the items like the Fund's performance record, Mutual fund scheme's portfolio of investment, scheme expense ratio, withdrawal facilities, and sponsor's past performance in terms of managing risk and return, Disclosure of investment objectives in offer documents and disclosure of NAV on every trading day. The qualities were ranked according to the preferences of investors by analysing mean and standard deviation. The data acquired based on the criteria adopted by the investors to judge the qualities of mutual funds considered are shown in Table 4 below:

Table 4

Mutual fund's qualities			
Qualities of Mutual funds	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank
Fund's Performance record	4.29	0.933	1
The scheme's portfolio of investment	4.27	0.885	2
Scheme expense ratio	3.80	1.057	5
Withdrawal facilities	3.79	1.163	6
Sponsor's past performance in terms of managing risk and return	3.92	1.094	4
Disclosure of investment objective in the offer document	3.93	1.172	3
Disclosure of NAV on every trading day	3.62	1.328	7

Source: Result of primary data analysis

The outcome of the data analysis presented in Table 4 depicts the qualities of mutual funds. From the statistical results, it is clear that the fund's performance record (mean 4.29, standard deviation 0.933, rank 1) is considered by investors as the most important quality of mutual funds. Scheme's portfolio of investment (mean 4.27, standard deviation 0.885, rank 2) is the next most important quality the investors consider. Disclosure of investment objective in the offer document (mean 3.93, standard deviation 1.172, rank 3) is also an important quality of mutual funds. The fourth and fifth criteria in terms of quality given by the investors are for the sponsor's past performance in terms of managing risk and return (mean 3.92, standard deviation 1.094, rank 4) and scheme expense ratio (mean 3.80, standard deviation 1.057, rank 5). The sixth and seventh qualities of investments are withdrawal facilities and disclosure of NAV on every trading day. Hence, it can be inferred that individual investors always give importance to the funds' performance record and the scheme's portfolio of investment. The least important thing is given to withdrawal facilities and disclosure of NAV on every trading day.

7. Conclusion

Mutual funds are trusts that pool the savings of multiple individuals with similar financial goals. Following this collection method, the funds are invested in securities, debentures, and other money market instruments. The income generated by these investments and the realised capital gains are distributed among the unit holders according to the number of units they possess. Investing in a professionally handled, diversified bundle of securities may be reasonable with mutual funds, making them an excellent choice for the typical investor. The individual investors in this study emphasised the accumulation of funds and meeting unexpected future events. The investors here considered mutual funds an ideal and preferred investment option. Investors invest their savings to get a better return from their investments. Better returns from mutual funds can be assured only by long-term investments. As with any type of investment, mutual fund investments are also affected by market risk. Investors are recommended to form the practice of regular saving in order to consistently generate higher returns during fluctuating market conditions, as small deposits will compound into a larger capital basis.

8. Implications of the study

The study results imply that investors consider return from investment and its safety as important factors while investing. They consider the performance record

of mutual funds while investing. To meet investors' expectations, mutual fund companies must develop their strategies effectively. Today's primary challenge for the mutual fund company is converting potential investors into active investors. At regular intervals, new and innovative schemes must be introduced to maintain investor confidence. The offer documents should specify the diversification of investment, which ensures the investors that the investment in mutual funds will generate a return in future. Improvement in the performance of mutual funds attracts more individuals to invest in mutual funds. Thus, it will also contribute to the mutual fund industry's general expansion and growth.

9. Scope for further study

This study solely looked at the characteristics, awareness, and variables that individual investors take into account while choosing investments. Individual investors usually make irrational decisions rather than rational decisions. So, for further research, a study can be conducted on the behavioural bias of individual investors on mutual fund investments. Also, a study can be made on the influence of financial advisors on investment decision-making.

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